

MUSIC AS A MEANS OF SPIRITUAL EDUCATION OF YOUTH

S.A. Akhmedova

Director of the 15th Children's Music and Art School of Olot District, Bukhara Region

Annotation: The article discusses issues such as the role and importance of music in schools, the musical creativity of Eastern scholars, and the importance of age characteristics in music education.

Keywords: education, musical education, spiritual education, mental state, emotions, musical culture, musical activities, musical perception, listening skills.

As is known, upbringing begins in the family, and then continues in preschool educational institutions and schools. Therefore, Article 8 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Education” entitled “Preschool Education and Training” states that “Preschool education and training is a type of education aimed at educating and training children, their intellectual, spiritual, moral, ethical, aesthetic and physical development, as well as preparing children for general secondary education” [1].

Chapter 3 of the Concept for the Development of the Preschool Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, entitled “Goals and Priority Areas for the Development of the Preschool Education System”, specifically emphasizes the issue of improving the artistic, aesthetic and musical education and educational level of preschool children, and introducing the basics of STEAM education from an early age [2].

In different historical periods, the problem of defining the goals and objectives of musical education and the spiritual development of children had its own solution. The goal, arising from the social system and ideology, was to educate a comprehensively developed personality, the core of which was the ideas of that era, moral norms, etc., in which musical education was considered not as a value, but only as a means.

It is known that education affects the human mind, emotions, imagination, worldview, and behavior. The art and language of music are understandable and close to everyone. The pedagogical scientist Qazoqboy Yuldoshev defines the concept of education as follows: “Education is a practical pedagogical process aimed at forming certain physical, mental, moral, and spiritual qualities in a person; a set of measures taken to ensure that a person has the characteristics necessary for living in society. Education is an eternal value that ensures human humanity. Without education, neither an individual

nor a human society can exist. Because the values that ensure the existence of a person and society are passed on from one generation to another only through education. In pedagogical literature, the term “Education” is used in broad and narrow meanings. In a broad sense, education means the sum of all influences, activities, actions, and aspirations aimed at forming a human personality, ensuring its active participation in the production and social, cultural, and educational life of society. In this understanding, education includes not only educational work carried out in the family, school, children's and youth organizations, but also the entire social system, its leading ideas, literature, art, cinema, radio, television, etc. Also, the concept of education in a broad sense includes education and information.

In a narrow sense, education means pedagogical activities aimed at the physical development of a person, his worldview, spiritual and moral image, and aesthetic taste. This is carried out by the family and educational institutions, as well as public organizations. Education and information are not included in education in a narrow sense. However, any education exists only in close connection with education. Because in the process of education and information, not only does a person's knowledge increase, but also the formation of his moral and spiritual qualities is accelerated.

Music is a type of art that occupies a wide place in our cultural life and is of great importance in the development of the human personality. The role of musical education in human life, in its growth and formation as a person is extremely large, and music is a constant companion of a person from the moment of birth, that is, from the time of infancy, when his mother sings to him, to the last days of his life, in moments of joy, sorrow, and peace. Music is such a science and art that it serves as a means of establishing communication between people through their mutual spiritual experiences and emotions.

The educational feature of music is that it reflects thoughts and feelings through sound vibrations and reflections, and expresses moral problems that have been stirring humanity at various stages of life. This also reveals the philosophical essence of music. It has the ability to have a strong impact on human emotions and is a proven means of moral and ideological education of young people.

Musicologists, thinkers, and scientists have long expressed their opinions about the unlimited possibilities of music's influence on the human spiritual world. They tried to determine the characteristics of music among the arts that affect the formation of a person as a person. Ancient thinkers emphasized the great importance of musical education for the growing generation.

Abu Nasr al-Farabi's works "Kitabul-musiqy al-kabir" ("The Great Book of Music"), "Kitabul-musiqy" ("The Book of Music"), "Kitabun fi-ihsa'il-iqa" ("The Book on the Classification of Musical Rhythms"), "Kalamu fil-musiqy" ("The Book on the Styles of Music") and others testify to his thorough mastery of music theory. Al-Farabi, first of all, emphasized its positive qualities in the formation of a person's moral qualities, writing: "Music is useful in the sense that it regulates the character of those who have lost their balance, perfects those who have not reached perfection, and maintains the balance of those who are in balance."

Abu Raykhan al-Biruni's thoughts on the rules of conduct inherent in human life and life are of great pedagogical importance. He says that a person can achieve true perfection only if he is beautiful both internally and externally. He equates modesty and moderation with nobility. He emphasizes that a person must always adhere to these [3]. Abu Ali ibn Sina believes that the body and soul are inextricably linked in a person, that if any illness occurs in the body, the soul also suffers, and, most importantly, that music is a means of communication, and recommends the effective use of instruments such as the tanbur, gijjak, nai, and chang in the treatment of people with mental illnesses. Describing music as a powerful educational tool that affects the spiritual and physical nature of a person, he put forward the idea that it is important to educate a child's musical sense from a very young age - this strengthens the mental state.

Music has a particularly wide range of possibilities for expressing mental states. Human mood is a complex feeling, it is not connected with anything. The power of music is that it can express joy, sadness, imagination, courage, depression and similar human mental states in a private and general way, in their interdependence and absorption into each other.

Music has a comprehensive effect on a person, and the melody and its musical expression deeply affect a person's emotions, awakening various feelings in him, forming various moods. The text and ideological content of the song affect not only emotions, but also the minds of the listeners. It excites them and encourages them to think and observe. It evokes in people a certain attitude towards the spiritual problems reflected in the work. Such an effect is extremely complex and strong.

Music, musical activities affect not only the child's psyche, mood, character, aesthetic development, but also his physiological, general organism. When a child listens to music, sings, dances, his whole organism, including the respiratory tract, muscles, blood circulation, nervous system and other organs, is activated. Many of our physiologists have worked on this issue and have provided a lot of information in their research.

According to them, even the perinatal period has been proven to be very important for subsequent development. The music that a future mother listens to affects the mental development of the child. Most medical and psychological studies have shown that musical activity affects respiratory and circulatory functions, immune processes, brain function and the interaction of hemispheres, mental confirms that it has a positive effect on activity, psychomotor, speech development and computational abilities.

As a result of musical exposure, the following is achieved:

- the sensitivity of not only listening, but also visual analyzers increases;
- mental processes - attention, understanding, perception, memorization, recall, repetition improve;
- metabolic processes are regulated;
- the level of excitement, anxiety decreases.

Researchers who have studied the psychophysiological aspect of the effect of music have identified the following facts. The significant effect of music on the minute can be observed in blood volume, heart rate, blood pressure, blood sugar levels, as well as in muscle changes and the manifestation of emotions.

Thus, musical education is of great importance for the formation and development of a child, which gradually develops in the system of continuous education and is harmoniously improved with other types of education.

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